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Life Cycle Assessment: Adhesives industry

Supervisor/s

Bostik: Axelle-Beverly GUIRAND
UNIBA: Prof. Francesco NOCITO
CUT: Prof. Izabela CZEKAJ

Degree candidate

Delfina BANDIERA
Student ID (Matricola): 827363

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0. Contents

0. Contents	1
List of figures.....	2
List of tables.....	2
List of acronyms.....	2
1. Abstract	3
2. Introduction	4
2.1. Adhesives industry.....	4
2.2. Life Cycle Assessment.....	5
3. State-of-the-art	7
4. Materials and methods	12
5. Results and discussion	13
5.1. Overview of Resource Use assessment.....	13
5.1.1. Key concepts.....	13
5.1.2. Main issues.....	16
5.2. LCIA Methodologies.....	17
5.2.1. Environmental mechanism and impact pathway.....	17
5.2.2. EF 3.1: ADP-CML methodology.....	20
5.2.3. EN 15804 + A2.....	26
5.2.4. Prospects.....	29
5.3. 'Resource use' impact in the adhesives' industry.....	30
5.3.1. Resource Use (RU) in the Adhesives industry.....	30
5.3.2. Analysis of results.....	33
6. Conclusion	41
7. References	42

List of figures

Figure 1. EF 3.1. Framework of impact categories for characterisation modelling.	8
Figure 2. Comparison of bio and fossil-based polyester resins, from Ecoinvent 3.11.	9
Figure 3. Material flow and Impact Mechanism Overview.	18
Figure 4. Overview of characterization methods. Extracted from Sonderegger et al. [11]	20
Figure 5. Common raw materials and products' impact on RU, fossils, grouped by function	32
Figure 6. Common raw materials and products' impact on RU, minerals and metals, grouped by function.	33
Figure 7. Relative frequency histogram for Resource Use, fossils.....	34
Figure 8. Relative frequency histogram for Resource Use, minerals and metals.....	34
Figure 9. Main contributors and other widely used metals.	38

List of tables

Table 1. Reserve definitions.....	15
Table 2. Resource Use impact category indicator according to EF 3.1. [13]	21
Table 3. Parameters describing resource use. Extracted from EN 15802: 2012 + A2: 2019...27	
Table 4. Adhesives general formulation.	31
Table 5. Statistical parameters of Resource Use impact category	34

List of acronyms

ADP	Abiotic Depletion Potential
CF	Characterization Factor
CML	Institute of Environmental Sciences of the University of Leiden
EF	Environmental Footprint
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ILCD	International Reference Life Cycle Data System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PCF	Product Carbon Footprint
RU	Resource Use
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WRI	World Resources Institute

1. Abstract

This thesis investigates the Resource Use (RU) impact category within the broader framework of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), with focused application to the adhesives industry. The analysis adheres to the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 methodology as recommended by the European Commission, emphasizing the Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) indicators for fossil resources, minerals, and metals. The work offers a critical review of the conceptual and methodological development of these indicators, drawing attention to ongoing challenges—such as ambiguities in resource availability definitions, inconsistent data sources, and the insufficient integration of anthropogenic stocks and dissipative losses in current assessment models.

In addition to this methodological overview, the study includes a statistical evaluation of commonly used raw materials in construction adhesives, based on datasets from Ecoinvent and LCA for Experts. The results indicate a strong dependence on fossil resources, mainly linked to feedstocks and energy-intensive processes, while the contribution of minerals and metals remains comparatively low, although subject to methodological uncertainties. Furthermore, by linking raw material data to product-level assessments, the thesis demonstrates that formulation choices and process characteristics have a decisive influence on the final environmental profile of adhesives.

In summary, the findings highlight the necessity of broadening environmental assessment beyond the traditional focus on greenhouse gas emissions. Integrating transparent and robust resource use indicators into LCA emerges as a crucial step for enhancing result interpretation, minimizing burden shifting, and supporting eco-design initiatives. Such integration also aids industrial decision-making and facilitates more consistent communication of sustainability performance across the chemical value chain. Ultimately, this thesis provides statistical reference values to interpret RU indicators effectively and identifies key methodological limitations that must be addressed to improve their reliability.

2. Introduction

Environmental studies such as Product Carbon Footprint (PCF), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), and Material Flow Analysis (MFA), among others, are increasingly essential for companies and organizations committed to sustainability, especially for those seeking to remain competitive in the chemical sector. Among these, LCA is one of the most widely applied due to the holistic perspective it provides on product systems. Since this thesis is based on LCA, the report begins by introducing the assessment methodology and reviewing the state of the art in the adhesives industry. The primary objective of this thesis is to address specific challenges related to environmental assessment within this sector.

First, the study highlights the importance of evaluating all relevant environmental indicators, beyond greenhouse gas emissions, and discusses how practitioners currently address data scarcity. Second, to illustrate both the complexity and the value of detailed indicator analysis, this thesis focuses on the impact category Resource Use. The study is based on bibliographic research on LCA and environmental guidelines, analysis of data from databases, and insights from current practices in a major company within the adhesives and sealants industry.

2.1. Adhesives industry

The adhesives industry is framed in the specialty chemicals sector, focused on the production of formulated compounds designed to bond two or more substrates. Whether they are derived from natural or synthetic feedstocks, adhesives are generally polymer- or resin-based (e.g., polyurethane, epoxy, acrylics, polyvinyl acetate) and combined with additives such as tackifiers and stabilizers to optimize their performance [30]. It must be mentioned that sealants are often marketed alongside adhesives, as they also provide adhesion while filling and sealing cracks or joints. Common sealants include silicone, acrylic, urethane, butyl, and other polymeric types.

Positioned in the downstream segment of the chemical value chain, the adhesives industry relies primarily on basic chemicals and intermediates from the petrochemical sector, although bio-sourced adhesives are gaining relevance. Adhesives have numerous applications, including packaging, construction, automotive, electronics, furniture, and consumer goods.

The most demanded technologies are water-based systems, followed by solvent-based, hot melt, pressure-sensitive, and reactive systems [25]. The industry faces increasing pressure to improve environmental performance, reduce volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions, and adopt circular economy strategies. This explains why the demand for water-based and reactive systems is rising, while for solvent-based systems is declining. R&D teams developing solutions to address these trends are supported by LCA practitioners in the identification of alternatives that are less impactful on the environment and the communication of reductions to customers.

Although this study focuses on the adhesives and sealants industry, many of the issues discussed are relevant for the whole chemical sector. What distinguishes the adhesives industry is its position closer to the consumer-end of the value chain, unlike primary sectors such as petrochemicals, which are nearer to resource extraction. This positioning has important implications for data collection, as it increases the number of actors that must collaborate in providing raw material information to carry out accurate environmental assessments.

2.2. Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) stands out as a key methodology for evaluating the environmental impact of a product or service across its entire life cycle. A comprehensive LCA quantifies emissions, resource consumption, and related environmental and health impacts associated with a product system. Depending on the scope, LCA can cover a product's entire life cycle—from resource extraction, manufacturing, and processing, through use and retail, to disposal, including transportation at all stages [4]. By analysing these interactions, LCA facilitates the identification of a broad spectrum of environmental impacts, such as contributions to global warming or eutrophication, along with their sources, and prevents burden shifting between life cycle stages, impact categories, or product alternatives.

For the adhesives and sealants industry, LCA provides a science-based foundation to guide environmental improvements along the value chain, ensure regulatory compliance, support R&D, and enable customers to make more sustainable choices.

LCA studies rely on diverse data describing global supply chains, including technical specifications, market and trade flows. Collecting such data is particularly challenging in the adhesives industry due to the specificity and diversity of formulations, most of which are not

disclosed, and the multiple manufacturing pathways involved. This issue becomes even more significant when the formulation includes biobased or bioprocessed materials, usually novel products for which generic and representative data is not available. Adhesives and sealants often contain a mix of polymers, additives, and solvents sourced from various chemical producers worldwide. Differences in energy sources, feedstocks, and manufacturing practices at each production site result in significant variability in environmental performance. Accurate, site-specific data is therefore essential to ensure LCA studies reflect the true environmental footprint of adhesives and provide reliable sustainability guidance [24].

According to ISO 14040:2006, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is composed by four main stages: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory analysis, life cycle impact assessment, and interpretation. These are usually described as consecutive, but they are actually part of an iterative process. This thesis first outlines current industry practices and the main challenges faced by practitioners, particularly the limitations of restricted assessments and data collection within the inventory stage. It then provides a detailed analysis of the Resource Use impact category and concludes with the interpretation of results.

When discussing LCA, it is important to consider study parameters, such as regional, temporal, and technological representativeness, as well as the life cycle stages included. The two most common approaches are cradle-to-grave, which covers the entire life cycle from resource extraction to disposal, and cradle-to-gate, which assesses impacts up to the factory gate. In the chemical industry, cradle-to-gate results are generally preferred due to the wide variety of product applications, which increase the complexity of the study in the use-stage. This is also the case for the adhesives industry, except where regulations require full LCAs, such as Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) under EN15804+A2 for construction-related adhesives. Unless otherwise specified, the scope used in this thesis is cradle-to-gate.

3. State-of-the-art

LCA is the most widely applied methodology for assessing environmental impacts of products, processes, or services within defined system boundaries. Its framework is established by ISO 14040:2006 — Life Cycle Assessment — Principles and Framework — and ISO 14044:2006 — Requirements and Guidelines, supported by additional guidelines and standards such as the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook and ISO 14067, which addresses product carbon footprints.

In alignment with these standards, several life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methods translate inventory flows into numerical results, often referred to as impact scores or indicators. The most used methodologies are EN15804+A2 (EU construction sector), EF v3.1, NMD Bepalingsmethode (Dutch construction sector), and ReCiPe 2016. Each method prioritizes different impact categories, and their reported values are often not directly compatible, even though they comply with the underlying standards [28]. This lack of consensus is a major obstacle to widespread LCA adoption and communication.

To harmonize and facilitate LCA application, the European Commission's Joint Research Centre developed the Environmental Footprint methodology for Products and Organizations (PEF and OEF, respectively). These methods provide detailed guidance for modelling, calculating, and reporting life cycle environmental impacts. The EF database, currently version 3.1 (2022), translates inventory flows into indicators for different impact categories, which can then be interpreted across environmental areas (Figure 1). The aggregation into areas of impact is a simplification for interpretive purposes and should not be taken as prescriptive.

Figure 1. EF 3.1. Framework of impact categories for characterisation modelling.

This thesis adopts the EF as the main framework, given its widespread use in consumer information and B2B communication, even outside the EU. As the construction sector is a key market for adhesives and sealants, EN15804+A2, “Sustainability of construction works — Environmental Product Declarations — Core rules for the product category of construction products,” is also addressed [20]. EN15804’s LCIA method aligns with EF v3.1, sharing impact assessment models, indicator units, and characterization factors (CFs), differing only in CFs for biogenic CO₂ uptake and emissions, which are not analysed in this work [27].

In addition to standards, LCA practitioners often rely on industrial guidelines to implement practical studies. Common examples include the Product Carbon Footprint Guideline for the Chemical Industry – Together for Sustainability (TfS, 2022 [21]), and the Pathfinder Framework – Guidance for the Accounting and Exchange of Product Life Cycle Emissions 2.0 – World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD, 2023 [23]).

Nowadays, as shown by the focus of the industrial guidelines, emphasis is made only on emissions accountings. Companies typically report only greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, in the form of Product Carbon Footprint (PCF), based on ISO 14067. The PCF sums GHG emissions and removals expressed as CO₂ equivalents, analogous to calculating only the Climate Change category in EF 3.1 using the IPCC 2021 methodology (Global Warming Potential). While simplifying analysis and communication, this approach provides a limited view of a product's overall environmental performance and may overlook trade-offs or co-benefits between impacts [21].

Beyond carbon emissions, assessing resource consumption and pollution during manufacturing is critical to avoid burden shifting [4]. For example, promoting bio-based products solely for their lower PCF can overlook increased environmental pressures on land use or eutrophication. These trade-offs become evident only in a complete LCA, as illustrated in Figure 2, which compares LCIA results of polyester resin from soy and fossil feedstocks (data from Ecoinvent 3.11).

Figure 2. Comparison of bio and fossil-based polyester resins, from Ecoinvent 3.11.

The predominant focus on GHG emissions is not a matter of negligence but rather a consequence of the time- and resource-intensive nature of assessing all impact categories. In addition, public awareness and demand for reporting impacts beyond GHG emissions remain limited. Methodologies for other categories are more complex and less standardized, often leading to heterogeneous and sometimes unreliable results. To highlight the importance of broadening the scope of studies beyond GHG emissions—and to illustrate the variety of factors that influence each indicator—this thesis examines the Resource Use impact

categories. These categories are particularly relevant for the adhesives industry, where fossil resources are extracted both as feedstocks for the main chemical platforms and as energy carriers for manufacturing, while metals and minerals are required in most formulations.

Before moving forward, it is important to address a final key challenge currently faced by LCA practitioners: the lack of sufficient third-party data. As discussed earlier, the adhesives industry's position in the chemical value chain makes it highly dependent on upstream actors for LCA studies. These impacts fall under Scope 3 activities—emissions and impacts that occur in the value chain but are not directly controlled by the reporting company. Among them, raw material extraction represents one of the largest contributors to the environmental footprint of adhesives [21]. However, measuring this impact is also one of the most difficult tasks since accurate results depend on cooperation across multiple actors along the value chain. In the absence of global methodological agreements, suppliers calculate impacts using different guidelines and exchange business-to-business information that is not mutually comparable. Despite ongoing efforts, most suppliers currently provide only the PCF. Consequently, LCA practitioners aiming to perform a full LCA must identify the most appropriate way to estimate the remaining environmental indicators, often based on multiple assumptions.

Due to this obstacle, data collection has become one of the most time-consuming and demanding phases of LCA. To construct the inventory, practitioners gather available information on purchased raw materials, energy and water consumption, and emissions to air, land, or water by substance. For processes directly controlled by the company, data generally comes from primary sources (specific to on-site processes, often measured directly). For activities outside the company's direct control, data is usually secondary (industry averages, literature-based estimates, associations, published production data, government statistics, third-party LCI databases, engineering studies, or patents). Secondary data can be of comparable quality to primary data, depending on how closely the proxy represents the actual process.

When collecting raw material data from suppliers, gaps are common and must be addressed through proxy searches or process modeling. Proxy data is drawn from similar processes, extrapolated, and customized to increase representativeness. By using proxies or modeling, the practitioner aims to ensure the closest possible match with the target process in terms of geographical, technological, and temporal representativeness. To achieve this, various sources of information are consulted, including Safety and Technical Data Sheets,

patents, supplier websites or direct exchanges with them, scientific publications, and Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs). Most of the work, however, relies on LCA database exploration. The most frequently consulted databases include Ecoinvent 3.11, LCA for Experts, Carbon Minds, ELCD, Industry Data 2.0, Agrifootprint, among others. Additionally, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has launched the Global LCA Data Access (GLAD) network, a system that enables finding and comparing datasets across multiple databases.

To evaluate the robustness of estimations, results can be compared with those of similar products or with data for the same raw material from different suppliers. In many cases, suppliers provide the PCF of the raw material, which can be cross-checked with the practitioner's own estimation. All collected data and assumptions must be transparently documented throughout the study, and their quality must be assessed and reported alongside the LCIA results.

As previously mentioned, once the inventory phase is completed, the collected data is transformed into environmental indicators using methodologies specific to each impact category, as illustrated in Figure 1. The remainder of this work focuses on the subsequent phases: Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) and the interpretation of results.

4. Materials and methods

As explained in the previous sections, this thesis is based on the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 methodology, aligned with ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006. This section focuses on the analysis of the Resource Use impact category. It begins with a bibliographic review to clarify the scope of this category and to trace the methodological developments that led to its current assessment framework.

Although understanding the applied methodology is of utmost importance, it must be acknowledged that this step is currently automated by LCA software. In practice, practitioners enter inventory data into the program, which then calculates the indicator values internally, using characterization factors provided in the standards' reference documents. As a result, the added value of an LCA lies primarily in the interpretation of the results. To achieve this, practitioners must be able to contextualize outcomes within a reasonable range, compare them with average values for similar substances, and identify anomalies. However, a review of the literature for this impact category revealed a lack of guidance to support result interpretation, such as information on typical orders of magnitude for each indicator.

To address this gap, the second part of this study focuses on data analysis. Common raw materials in the adhesives and sealants industry—specifically for the construction sector—were identified and examined through consultation with industry LCA practitioners and bibliographic sources. Their LCIA values were obtained from multiple references. Most of the data originates from the Ecoinvent 3.11 and LCA for Experts databases, with the aim of using generic information, while product-level impacts were extracted from published Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) of commercial construction adhesives and sealants. The software used to perform the LCIA was SimaPro.

The focus on the construction sector is justified by the greater availability of non-confidential data compared to other application fields, given the requirement to publish EPDs. The Resource Use results of these raw materials were analyzed statistically, and the identified trends were interpreted to provide an overview of the current situation. However, the full dataset information cannot be disclosed due to confidentiality protection.

Finally, the impacts of the raw materials are linked to the LCIA of the selected construction adhesives, enabling the identification of key contributors and clarifying the relationship between formulation and final product.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Overview of Resource Use assessment

The ability of today's society to fulfil our needs, as well as future generations' possibilities to fulfil their own, strongly depends on natural resources. Respecting the principle of sustainability implies ensuring that resource availability for future generations is at least as favourable as it is today. Conducting a comprehensive Resource Use (RU) assessment is essential to avoid burden shifting and biased conclusions, particularly when assessing emerging technologies. For example, when comparing petrochemical and bio-based production routes for the same product, the high consumption of fossil resources and associated GHG emissions in the former may lead to the assumption that bio-based alternatives are always more sustainable. However, bio-based systems often require significant inputs of energy for biomass pretreatment and conversion—derived from fossil sources— or catalysts based on scarce metals, which may lead to significant resource use as well. In some cases, this could result in greater overall environmental impacts than the petrochemical route, as shown in Figure 2.

This section lays the conceptual foundations to ensure understanding of Resource Use impact category, introducing the main underlying concepts and issues. As this bibliographic research is built on the Environmental Footprint 3.1, major efforts are invested in describing the parameters that lead to the currently recommended indicator: the Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP), developed by the CML in 2002.

5.1.1. Key concepts

To begin with, it is essential to clarify what is meant as “resources” in the context of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). A resource is defined by its intrinsic value or utility for a specific purpose [1]. Generally, this value is associated to the ability to provide a function beneficial to humans from an anthropogenic perspective. These functions range from the satisfaction of specific needs (e.g. the properties of a material for a production process) to the contribution to the overall human well-being (e.g. cultural) and economy. From this perspective, not all material flows within the system are considered resources. For example, contaminated effluents are only regarded as resources if they are remediated and can potentially be further valorised.

Resources can be categorized in various ways, leading to different assessment approaches [2]. First, they can be classified based on their origin:

- Abiotic resources: Inorganic materials (e.g. water and metals) and organic materials that are no longer part of the biosphere due to the time elapsed since their biological origin (e.g., fossil fuels).
- Biotic resources: Derived from organisms that are alive or recently deceased at the time of extraction (e.g. wood)

Secondly, resources can be categorised by their regeneration capacity:

- Stock or deposits: These have a finite quantity and are either not regenerated (metals in ores) or regenerated at a negligible rate (e.g. fossil resources).
- Funds: These are regenerated but can still be depleted, like the stock resources, if the rate of extraction exceeds the rate of regeneration. Depletion can be either temporary or permanent. For instance, soil can support plant growth continuously, but excessive use or erosion can degrade it. Groundwater is also a typical example.
- Flows: provided as a continuous flow (e.g. solar radiation, wind and to some extent freshwater) and can be harvested as they flow by. They cannot be globally depleted but there may be local or temporal low availability.

While flows are continuously regenerated, funds can be regenerated within human timeframes, and stocks cannot [3]. Thus, stock resources are typically classified as non-renewable, while fund and flow resources are collectively regarded as renewable.

The various impacts associated to the extraction and use of resources can be linked to the Area of Protection (AoP) “Natural Resources”, and to some extent to the “Natural Environment”. In this case, the focus lies on the availability of these resources, a topic of ongoing debate that is further explored in the following section. However, it should be noted that not all resources affect these AoPs in the same manner. For instance, metal ores become dispersed through use, fossil resources are consumed, and water is only temporarily withdrawn from circulation [4]. Therefore, resources must be grouped under common environmental mechanisms to enable consistent assessment.

Modern society depends on all types of resources –not only abiotic resources, but also natural assets. Among abiotic resources, water and land are distinct due to their direct environmental impacts. As a result, they are evaluated within their own specific impact categories (i.e. Water Use and Land Use). In contrast, the assessment of biotic assets such as

biomass is not yet fully established. Consequently, the current scope of Resource Use (RU) category is limited to fossil fuels, minerals, and metals.

To fully understand the various methodologies developed for this impact category, it is necessary to distinguish between different types of reserves. While definitions vary depending on source and context, Table 1 provides an overview according to the Joint Research Centre (JRC, 2019) [7], one of the most recent state-of-the-art reports on Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA).

Table 1. Reserve definitions.

Terminology	Definition
Ultimate reserve or crustal content	Total amount of an element in a given layer of the Earth's crust. It is estimated by multiplying the average concentrations of chemical elements in the crustal layer by the mass of the same crustal layer. The crustal content of an element will never be extracted completely as some deposits/concentrations will remain unavailable under all foreseeable economic conditions.
Ultimately extractable reserve or extractable global resource	Amount of crustal content that will ultimately prove extractable by humans.
Reserve base	Concentration or occurrence of solid material of economic interest in or on the Earth's crust in such form, grade or quality, and quantity that there are reasonable prospects for eventual economic extraction. The location, quantity, grade or quality, continuity and other geological characteristics are known, estimated or interpreted from specific geological evidence and knowledge.
Economic reserve	Economically mineable part of a measured and/or indicated mineral resource or reserve base, at the time of determination.

Some additional clarifications are necessary before proceeding with the report. First, the term *mineral deposit* refers to a natural accumulation of minerals, which is not always economically viable to extract (e.g., a clay deposit). In a more restricted sense, *ore* refers to mineral deposits that are rich enough to be mined profitably for their valuable content (e.g., bauxite for aluminium). Finally, *metal* refers more precisely to the refined element or alloy extracted from ores (e.g., aluminium).

Several concepts are often used interchangeably in this context, though they represent distinct ideas and should be clearly differentiated [8]:

- *Depletion* refers to the physical reduction in a resource's presence on Earth, typically associated with geological or natural stocks.
- *Scarcity* indicates that the available quantity of a resource is or will soon be insufficient to meet demand.
- *Criticality* describes a resource that is both scarce and essential for modern society. Its evaluation includes economic, social, and geopolitical dimensions.

5.1.2. Main issues

Since the late 20th century, there has been an ongoing debate regarding the appropriate way to assess this impact category. The inability to define a universally "scientific" methodology has led to the development of various normative frameworks. Abiotic depletion presents a challenge that crosses the boundary between the economy and the environment, as resource reserves depend on future extraction technologies. Accordingly, there are multiple ways to define and quantify the issue [5]. This continued debate has driven the evolution of resource assessment methodologies, which will be examined in this bibliographic research.

One of the most challenging aspects of developing a suitable characterization model for resource use is establishing criteria to evaluate the criticality of one natural resource in relation to another. This evaluation is complicated by the constantly evolving functionalities and availability of resources, and by the difficulty of expressing these changes in terms of characterization factors.

As introduced, a primary issue derived from the principle of sustainability is the uncertainty surrounding the needs and capabilities of future generations, which will likely differ significantly from those of today. It is difficult to determine which resource functions

should be preserved, as new needs may emerge and current applications may become obsolete. For example, previous generations could not have anticipated the criticality of rare metals resulting from their crucial role in renewable energy and electronic devices [4]. Furthermore, there is ambiguity regarding what should be considered “available”, as this depends on the technological capabilities of both current and future societies, and on the temporal scope of the assessment.

There is a dynamic relationship between the demand for and availability of natural resources. When a resource becomes scarce, prices typically rise, which leads to a reduction in demand. This, in turn, can stimulate the development of substitutes, new technologies, and recycling techniques. It also encourages exploration of new reserves and advances in extraction technologies. As a result, both demand and availability are simultaneously influenced by technical, economic and social factors. These fluctuations directly affect the estimates of economic reserves and reserve bases, as defined in Table 1, and contribute to the instability of characterisation factors.

5.2. LCIA Methodologies

In response to the key issues discussed in the previous section, the LCA community has developed and refined various methodologies to assess the impact of resource use. These methodologies differ in several aspects: the conception of the environmental mechanism and characterisation model; the completeness of the scope; relevance and applicability; scientific robustness and uncertainty; and transparency and reproducibility.

A detailed account of the normative lies beyond the scope of this study. Nonetheless, certain elements relevant for understanding the current method are addressed.

5.2.1. Environmental mechanism and impact pathway

The environmental mechanism illustrated in Figure 3, describes flow of resources from their primary or natural source (the ecosphere or lithosphere) to their secondary or anthropogenic source (the technosphere). Resources are extracted from natural stocks — whose qualities vary according to the effort required for their extraction, as explained in Table 1— and enter the technosphere via mining and quarrying. There, they become raw materials and undergo various transformations, which render them either temporarily unavailable or permanently unrecoverable, depending on their nature.

Mineral resources are immobilised in products and infrastructure (collectively referred as *in-use stocks*) for varying durations—ranging from short-term (e.g., an aluminium can) to long-term (e.g., a steel bridge)—and qualities (e.g., pure metal vs. alloy). Through recycling or recovery, resources can be retained in use for longer periods. Once they are no longer in use, they are discarded with varying degrees of recoverability. Crucially, all stages are interconnected through a *dissipative flow*, defined as any usage that renders a mineral resource unrecoverable. This flow is represented by a dashed line, as the methodology to quantify it is still under development.

Figure 3. Material flow and Impact Mechanism Overview.

Material flow (grey layer) and impact mechanism overview. Depletion methods are shown in green, future effort methods in yellow, thermodynamic accounting methods in orange, supply risk methods in blue, and the “dilution of total stocks” approach in purple. Dashed flows represent concepts that are under discussion but not yet operational. Figure extracted from Sonderegger et al. [11]

In Figure 3, the parameters are colour-coded according to the impact mechanism they correspond to, which ultimately guides their characterisation models. The concentration of arrows around the resource extraction stage suggests that most characterisation models focus on this process.

In general terms, some methods model the depletion of natural stocks (green); others assess the extraction of exergy—the maximum useful work obtainable as the system reaches thermodynamic equilibrium with its environment, which requires the definition of a reference state (orange); and others evaluate the decline in ore grade and the resulting increase in ore requirements, energy use, or costs (yellow). Within the technosphere, another category (blue) addresses supply risk, considering the likelihood of supply disruption due to geopolitical and market factors—such as the concentration of production or political instability in producer countries (e.g., for rare earth elements). The endpoints of supply risk are conceptualised as impaired product performance and increased production costs.

Lastly, the “dilution of total stocks” approach (purple) focuses on dissipative flows, assuming that only dissipation into the ecosphere constitutes an absolute loss. It considers both natural and anthropogenic stocks, without accounting for dissipation within the technosphere [11].

While a full description of each method is beyond the scope of this report, Figure 4 provides a useful classification overview, which may be helpful when selecting appropriate methodologies for an LCA study.

The selection of a certain methodology should align with the goal and scope of the LCA. When certification is not the objective, alternative methods to the normative recommendation may be more appropriate. For example, in eco-design studies where short-term economic risks of raw material supply disruptions are more critical than the long-term depletion of mineral resources in the Earth’s crust, the ADP indicator may not be the most suitable. Recommendations for method selection according to application context are provided by Berger et al., 2020 [12].

Figure 4. Overview of characterization methods. Extracted from Sonderegger et al. [11]

Among the four main method categories, *depletion* and *future effort* methods are considered the most traditional LCIA approaches. In contrast, *thermodynamic accounting* and *supply risk* methods offer complementary information and may be useful for sensitivity analyses.

Currently, depletion methods are the most widely applied. The other categories are not recommended by the normative primarily due to two limitations: either they lack environmental relevance because they do not adequately capture resource scarcity, or they suffer from high uncertainty and instability in their characterisation factors [2].

5.2.2. EF 3.1: ADP-CML methodology

LCIA characterisation methods aim to model the environmental mechanism underlying an impact category, representing a cause-effect chain that begins with the environmental intervention (e.g. physical extraction) and extends to its potential impact. Characterisation factors are derived from this model.

The methodology currently recommended by the JRC is the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1. method [7]. According to EF 3.1., the two mandatory indicators for RU impact assessment are Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) for mineral and metal resources ($ADP_{ultimate\ reserves}$) and for energy carriers (ADP_{fossil}). This characterisation method was initially conceived in 1995 and subsequently refined by the Centre of Environmental Science of Leiden University (CML) in 2002 [3]. It was first recommended by the ILCD Handbook in 2010 [10] and adopted by its successor, the EF, in 2013 [6]. Further improvements were proposed by van Oers et al. in 2016 [5] and reaffirmed by JRC on several occasions, including in the 2023 update of CFs [13]. The following sections, as well as Table 2 describe the method as it is currently

implemented, with additional comments provided to clarify how it has evolved to its present form.

Table 2. Resource Use impact category indicator according to EF 3.1. [13]

Impact category	Resource Use
Characterisation model	Relation between the natural reserve of a resource and its rate of extraction.
AoP	Natural resources
Type	Midpoint indicator
Category indicator	(Decrease in) availability
Characterisation factor	Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP)
Region	Global
Time scale	Infinite
Method name	Resource Use, minerals and metals
Indicator	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)
Inventory input	Mass (kg) of element extracted from natural stocks
Indicator unit	kg of Sb eq. per functional unit
Number of CFs	48 (mostly metals and metalloids, only a few non-metal elements, excluding minerals and aggregates)
Method name	Resource use, fossil
Indicator	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)
Inventory input	Mass (kg) of fossil resource extracted from natural stocks
Indicator unit	MJ per functional unit
Number of CFs	6 (coal and brown coal, natural gas, peat, oil and uranium)

The geographical scale of this indicator is global, as the supply and demand for mineral and fossil resources are interconnected through global transport networks. While regional depletion may occur, such challenges can generally be mitigated through transportation. Ultimately, the issue becomes one of economic feasibility rather than environmental scarcity.

There is some confusion regarding the terminology used for this category indicator, which is sometimes referred to as Resource Depletion and at other times as Resource Use. This discrepancy results from ongoing discussions around the scope of the category. Current LCIA recommendations fail to capture the overall resource footprint, as they focus solely on depletable resources and exclude biotic or renewable ones. In response to this limitation, the concept of Resource Use is being promoted to expand the scope of future assessments.

Indicator subdivision

One of the major changes in the method was the subdivision of the indicator into two categories: minerals and metals, and fossil. Initially, all resources were considered together, but the developers soon recognized that these categories address different issues and split the indicator in 2009. Combining the categories had led to significant underestimation of energy resource depletion at the global scale [14]. The main difference between the two categories is the substitutability of their substances. Minerals and metals constitute a heterogeneous group, with specific properties that limit their exchangeability. Fossil resources, such as oil, natural gas, and coal, are generally considered full substitutes for energy carriers and materials. This is evident globally, as countries with abundant natural gas reserves tend to base their economies on it, while those with more petroleum resources favour oil. If one resource becomes scarce, society can switch to importing the other, given that the function provided by both is essentially the same.

A comparison of the two formulas employed for the calculation of the result show how this differentiation is translated into numbers.

5.2.2.1. Characterisation factors

As introduced previously, in compliance with EF 3.1, there are two mandatory indicators:

- Resource use – minerals and metals ($ADP_{ultimate\ reserves}$)

$$ADP_{ultimate\ reserve} = \sum ADP_i \times m_i \quad I$$

$$ADP_i = \frac{DR_i/R_i^2}{DR_{Sb}/R_{Sb}^2} \quad II$$

- Resource use – fossil (ADP_{fossil})

$$ADP_{fossil} = \sum E_i = \sum m_i \times LHV_i \quad III$$

Where,

ADP_i : abiotic depletion potential of resource i (kg Sb eq. / kg resource i);

m_i : quantity of resource I extracted (kg);

E_i : energy contained in the resource extracted.

R_i : ultimate reserve of resource I (kg);

DR_i : extraction rate of resource i , regeneration not considered ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$)

R_{sb} : ultimate reserve of the reference resource, antimony (kg);

DR_{sb} : extraction rate of the reference resource, antimony ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$).

LHV_i : lower heating value of the fossil resource (MJ/kg or MJ/m^3)

The value of this indicator is calculated by summing the individual contributions of each substance, which are obtained by multiplying the quantity of resource extracted by the corresponding characterization factor, as outlined in equations I and III.

Fossils' assessment

As a result of this subdivision, the fossil indicator has unique features. First, in the case of fossil resources, the indicator is based solely on the resource extracted from nature, with neither availability nor demand being considered. Second, fossil resources are treated as mutually substitutable energy carriers, and their extraction amounts can be directly aggregated by the energy contained in the resource, as shown in Equation III. The characterisation factor for all fossil resources is $1 \text{ MJ}/\text{MJ}$, and the indicator is expressed in MJ. When process data is inventoried in mass units, an additional calculation step is required, as shown in Equation III. The characterisation factor becomes the corresponding lower heating value (MJ/kg or MJ/m^3). Once the inventory data is converted into MJ, it can be aggregated as explained earlier.

Uranium is the only non-fossil resource in this category, and its inclusion has been debated. It was incorporated because its primary application is as an energy carrier, though it can also serve material purposes, just as fossil fuels can.

In this category, fossil resources are valued exclusively for their energy content. While their role as energy carriers is indeed predominant, it is important to recall that the petrochemical industry also relies on them as essential feedstocks. The quantities extracted for material purposes are therefore included in the indicator, although this contribution cannot be distinguished in the final result.

Minerals and metals' assessment

As introduced before, when it comes to minerals and metals', the key feature of their characterization method is the accounting of the resource availability. The ADP-CML model is based on use-to-resource ratio, a fact reflected in the calculation of characterization factors.

As shown in Equation II, the ADP_i results from the ratio between the extraction rate and the ultimate reserve of the resource, divided by the same ratio for the reference. The ultimate reserve is estimated by multiplying the average natural concentration of the resource in the primary extraction media (e.g. the earth's crust) by the mass or volume of this media. The reserve is squared to emphasize mathematically the difference between extracting 1 kg of a small resource and a larger one, even if the use-to-resource ratio is the same.

A central point of discussion throughout the model's entire history has been the definition of the reserve selected as reference for availability, as detailed in Table 1. There is still no consensus on this definition [6]. Initially, in 2002, the baseline method proposed using "ultimate reserve" – a use-to-stock approach based on the net presence of the resource in the environment, beyond our capacity to extract it. Later, the ILCD shifted to using "reserve base," which is related to the current availability of the resource (use-to-availability). However, developers from CML continued to advocate for the "ultimate reserve," which was eventually adopted by the EF. The rationale for this preference is that estimates of economic reserves and reserve base fluctuate over time, defined by economic considerations rather than depletion concerns, resulting in unstable estimates [11]. From a sustainability perspective, the "ultimately extractable reserve" is the most relevant estimate concerning depletion, as it considers future generations' capacity to extract resources. Unfortunately, due to its dependence on future extraction technologies, it can never be exactly determined. As a compromise, the ultimate reserve is considered the best proxy for long-term assessments because it is more stable over time and directly linked to environmental depletion.

The choice of antimony as reference substance is arbitrary; it was selected because it is the first element in the alphabet for which a complete set of necessary data (extraction rate and ultimate reserve) is available [5].

Initially, CML developers attempted to include mineral deposits and configurations, but their determination was not robust enough due to the variability in their properties, especially in terms of composition [3]. The inclusion of mineral ores and compounds would have expanded the number of substances to be inventoried and would have required unnecessary effort from practitioners. Therefore, in 2002, they decided to calculate characterisation factors only for elements to improve evaluation efficiency.

Reference data

Since its inception, ADP factors have primarily relied on data from the US Geological Survey (USGS). Additional sources include the British Geological Survey (BGS), the Mining Annual Review (Mining Journal), and Roskill Reports on Metals and Minerals. Data for fossil resources has been sourced from the World Resource Institute (WRI) and the International Energy Agency (IEA) [3]. and uranium data is from the World Nuclear Association (WNA).

Over time, characterisation factors have been updated as new data became available. While ultimate reserve data has remained relatively stable, periodic updates have been necessary for production rates, which change more rapidly according to societal and technological trends. For example, the discovery of new applications for rare materials has led to significant increases in extraction rates. The ADP may be based on a specific year (t) or an average/cumulative production over a given period.

The current CFs in EF 3.1. were adopted from the CML method v. 4.8 (2016), with only minor adaptations were made in EF 3.0 and 3.1 to align with ILCD/EF flow list properties and units [18]. These factors are based on yearly extractions of elements as compiled by the USGS, with extraction rates referring to 1999. The calculation of crustal content is based on data from 1924 to 2002 [17].

In 2020, CML developers published an update to the characterisation factors, covering 79 elements, but this update has not yet been adopted by the EF recommendations. Production data was primarily sourced from USGS, complemented by BGS for time series up to 2015. Only primary production data (directly from mining) was included, excluding secondary (recycled) materials. They essayed different strategies to approach the time-dependency of production rates: time series year by year; time series including a moving average up to that year; or time series on the base of the cumulative production up to that year.

5.2.2.2. Normalisation

For normalisation purposes, the category indicator results must be determined for a specified reference region and time period. This reference year does not necessarily coincide with the one used for production rates in CF calculations. Data for normalisation factors (NFs) is obtained from the same sources as CFs. For minerals and metals, data from the USGS (2011) and BGS (2017) is used, while data for fossil resources and uranium refers to 2013 [14].

It is crucial to note that several reference documents for this impact category caution that: *“The results of this impact category shall be interpreted with caution, because the results of ADP after normalization may be overestimated. The European Commission intends to develop a new method moving from depletion to dissipation model to better quantify the potential for conservation of resources”* [19]. Therefore, it is not recommended to draw significant conclusions based solely on normalisation result¹. Given that normalisation is discouraged, a detailed examination of the corresponding factors falls outside the scope of this bibliographic research.

5.2.3. EN 15804 + A2

In 2016, the European Commission requested that the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) align the impact assessment models of EN 15804 with the EF methodology. Consequently, EN 15804 now recommends the same characterization model and implements the same characterization factors previously outlined for the EF.

The standard specifies that the following disclaimer must accompany the indicator results: *“The results of this environmental impact indicator shall be used with care as the uncertainties of the results are high and as there is limited experience with the indicator”* [20]. This disclaimer does not apply to all indicators; therefore, it is important to keep it in mind when interpreting this specific impact category.

In addition to the Resource Use impact indicator, EN 15804+A2 includes a section related to the same Area of Protection (AoP). Section 7.2.4.2 of the standard lists ten mandatory indicators that describe resource use, which are presented in Table 3. These indicators must be included in each module declared in the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD).

¹ Arkema and Bostik LCA teams are not relying on these normalisation factors for now. Neither normalisation nor weighting stages are performed.

Table 3. Parameters describing resource use. Extracted from EN 15802: 2012 + A2: 2019.

Parameter	Abbreviation	Unit (per functional unit or per declared unit)
Use of renewable primary energy excluding renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	PERE (PERT- PERM)	MJ, net calorific value
Use of renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	PERM	MJ, net calorific value
Total use of renewable primary energy resources (primary energy and primary energy resources used as raw materials)	PERT	MJ, net calorific value
Use of non-renewable primary energy excluding non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	PENRE (PENRT- PENRM)	MJ, net calorific value
Use of non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	PENRM	MJ, net calorific value
Total use of non-renewable primary energy resources (primary energy and primary energy resources used as raw materials)	PENRT	MJ, net calorific value
Use of secondary material	SM	kg
Use of renewable secondary fuels	RSF	MJ, net calorific value
Use of non-renewable secondary fuels	NRSF	MJ, net calorific value
Net use of freshwater	FW	m ³

This table is directly derived from the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), without any additional factors or calculations beyond the addition or subtraction of material flows.

The first six parameters focus on primary energy resources, categorized by regeneration rate (renewable/non-renewable) and final use. The categories “use of renewable/non-renewable primary energy excluding renewable/non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials” can be calculated by subtracting the input of energy resources used as raw materials from the total input of primary energy. For example, in the petrochemical industry, petroleum is a primary input (non-renewable energy resource), with a portion embedded in the final product and the remainder consumed to power equipment.

To calculate PENRM, the amount of petroleum used as feedstock is multiplied by its lower heating value (LHV), and this value is subtracted from the total petroleum consumption to obtain PENRE.

If a material is initially used as a raw material and its energy content is later utilized as an energy carrier within the product system, it should be classified as energy used as an energy carrier to avoid double counting. This change in status can be identified in the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) if data is reported by life cycle stage. For example, if the resource is first used for packaging, it would be accounted for as PENRM during the production stages. If it is subsequently incinerated with energy recovery, it should then be reclassified under PENRE in the use and application stages.

The second section of the table, covering secondary materials and fuels, provides information for analysing the product's circularity rate. The term "secondary material" refers to waste—any residue from production, transformation, or use, including substances, materials, or products that the holder intends to dispose of—that can be reused, recycled, or repurposed before final disposal [21]. For instance, packaging recycled from another process would be counted as secondary material, biodiesel from used cooking oil as secondary renewable fuel, and recovered oil from industrial waste as non-renewable. Due to the difficulty in tracking these flows, they are often not declared in EPDs.

Finally, the last parameter accounts for total freshwater use, excluding the portion that is returned—such as water used in closed-loop systems.

These indicators are essential for evaluating the environmental performance of construction products, offering a more comprehensive view of resource consumption than a single-score impact category. By analysing the inventory values, it becomes possible to disaggregate and expand the interpretation of the Resource Use indicator. This approach enables more detailed analysis by differentiating the source and general utility of the extracted resources. Moreover, the table extends beyond fossil and mineral resources—which would fall under non-renewable primary energy resources—to include renewable sources and freshwater consumption.

The analysis of these disaggregated indicators helps identify environmental hotspots and supports the implementation of measures aimed at optimizing overall environmental performance.

5.2.4. Prospects

Numerous normative reviews were conducted by the JRC, and on each occasion, the ADP-CML method was selected as the best available option [7][14][15]. This selection is based on the method's superior ability to reflect the decreasing resource availability, its robustness and its long history of use. Additionally, it enjoys the highest stakeholder acceptance and the lowest uncertainty. These claims are only valid among the other methods available for the same category at the time of evaluation and may not be true in comparison to other impact categories that are, certainly, more robust and certain. Its main weaknesses include the need for periodical updates to characterisation factor and the availabilities estimates. Ultimately, it does not fully capture actual resource depletion, as it fails to account for anthropogenic stocks.

Taking everything into account, there is a clear demand for more robust, dynamic, and representative characterization methods [7]. The characterization factors (CFs) need to be updated more frequently to reflect current production trends and future needs, and a broader range of inventory flows should be considered, particularly in terms of minerals and aggregates [12].

The indicator for abiotic resource depletion refers to the (decrease in) availability. As discussed throughout this report, the goal of this category assessment is to preserve the functions provided by resources. To do that, resources need to be available both for present and future generations. However, determining availability presents a complex challenge both in terms of location and temporality.

From a sustainability perspective, resource depletion is avoided as long as sufficient quantities remain in the economic stock. Therefore, this stock should be included when assessing resource availability, rather than focusing solely on natural reserves. This approach recognizes recycling and recovery as viable strategies for future generations, more accurately reflecting real-world conditions.

The concentration of a resource in its stock can be considered a direct measurement of its quality and functionality. Once a resource is extracted from its natural stock, it undergoes a series of transformations that concentrate it into primary materials, such as purified sand. This initial concentration process is reversed during the use stage, as economic processes (production, use, and disposal) dilute the element by combining it with other

materials and dispersing it within the technosphere. Consequently, the reduction in resource concentration renders it unavailable for future functions. For fossil fuels, this process is irreversible, as they are converted into carbon dioxide, water, and energy. In contrast, most minerals and metals are not irreversibly lost after use; they are merely dispersed. Some experts argue that mineral resources are not necessarily lost after extraction from the natural stock, as they can be recycled or recovered from the technosphere and reused.

This concept leads to the dissipation model, under which resources are considered consumed only if converted to an irrecoverable state, referred to as dissipative or dilution loss. Resources are dissipated either in the environment—sometimes referred to as emissions—or within the technosphere. In the latter case, resources may be found in products in use or in final waste disposal facilities. Several constraints can render a resource inaccessible to future generations, including changes in physicochemical properties, low concentrations and widespread distribution, chemical and mineralogical compositions (e.g., presence of contaminants), heterogeneity, and limited knowledge of the composition and location of sinks, all of which hinder the resource's recovery potential [1].

To illustrate this concept, consider the example of copper as a mineral resource. Once extracted as chalcopyrite rock, it is further concentrated and used in various products. When employed in pesticide production, its use is dissipative because recovery is not feasible; the copper becomes too dispersed in the soil and plants. However, when used to manufacture pipes, recovery is relatively easy, so it can be considered non-dissipative.

While the dissipation model is more realistic, it is more complex to assess. For it to be operational, Life Cycle Inventories (LCIs) must include information about dissipative losses in addition to the currently reported extraction rates. This implies that more follow-up data on product use and end-of-life stages is needed than is currently available. None of the methods implemented today incorporate these factors, but the JRC has indicated that it is developing methodologies to include them, as cited in the previous section [19].

5.3. 'Resource use' impact in the adhesives' industry

5.3.1. Resource Use (RU) in the Adhesives industry

Following the methodological framework outlined in the previous chapter, this section analyses the RU indicator results for some of the most common raw materials employed in the adhesives and sealants industry. The analysis is focused on the construction sector, where

LCA is more advanced due to strict regulations and the disclosure of information through published EPDs.

The adhesives industry covers a wide range of applications and manufacturing technologies, resulting in a highly diversified matrix of raw materials. Formulations are typically developed for specific applications and marketed in those terms, without disclosing the content of the product, which makes it more difficult to provide precise data while addressing general trends. For this reason, results are presented by grouping raw materials according to their functional role in adhesives, so that they can be compared with the corresponding product-level impacts.

In general, adhesives contain the components summarised in Table 4, though their proportions vary significantly. Some substances also fulfil multiple functions. The purpose of this overview is not to provide exhaustive formulations but rather to establish a reference framework for analysing raw material consumption and impacts.

Table 4. Adhesives general formulation.

Component	Function	Examples	Typical range
Binder	Provides adhesion and cohesion (core of the adhesive)	Epoxy resins, polyvinyl acetate (PVA), polyurethane (PU), acrylics, natural rubber, cements	20-60 %
Fillers	Modify mechanical properties, reduce cost, improve viscosity/thermal resistance	Calcium carbonate, clay, silica	5-40 %
Solvents/carriers	Dissolve or disperse the binder	Water (water-based adhesives); acetone, toluene, ethanol (solvent-based adhesives)	10-70 %
Plasticizers	Increase flexibility and reduce brittleness	Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate (DINCH), diisononyl phthalate (DINP)	1– 15 %
Pigments	Provide colour and opacity	Carbon black, metal oxides	0– 5 %
Other additives	Modify properties (e.g., tackifiers, hardeners, stabilisers)	Surfactants, polydimethylsiloxane, ethylene glycols	0– 5 %

The analysis comprises the production of 1 kg of commonly used raw materials—mainly for water-based polymer dispersion adhesives, polyurethane, and silane-modified polymer-based products—from cradle-to-gate. Packaging and transport of the final product

are not included. In addition, the impacts of four common construction adhesives and sealants were examined. These results were extracted from published EPDs, covering the process stage: raw materials supply (A1), transport (A2) and manufacturing (A3).

Most LCIA data for raw materials was obtained from the databases Ecoinvent 3.11 and LCA for Experts. Specific dataset nomenclature and commercial product names are not disclosed due to confidentiality restrictions. It must be clarified that the products presented belong to one of the global leaders in adhesives solutions, they do not correspond to industrial averages. The resulting indicators are presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5. Common raw materials and products' impact on RU, fossils, grouped by function.

Figure 6. Common raw materials and products' impact on RU, minerals and metals, grouped by function.

5.3.2. Analysis of results

Interpreting LCIA results is essential to verify the internal coherence of the study and to generate insights that can inform process improvements. This section identifies which resources significantly contribute to impacts, establishes reference values for comparison, and highlights key trends.

A common assumption might be that the most consumed resources generate the highest impacts, given that the indicator is proportional to the extracted quantity. However, this is not always the case, as the characterization factors applied to each resource vary considerably and affect the impact per kilogram extracted.

5.3.2.1. Statistical analysis

To identify general trends, a statistical analysis was performed on 36 raw materials, most of which are included in Figure 5 and Figure 6, and relevant parameters, following descriptive statistics [31], were calculated (Table 5). The results are discussed separately for each subcategory.

Figure 7. Relative frequency histogram for Resource Use, fossils.

Figure 8. Relative frequency histogram for Resource Use, minerals and metals.

Table 5. Statistical parameters of Resource Use impact category

Parameter	RU, fossils	RU, minerals and metals
Range	[0; 120]	[1E-10; 1E-03]
Mode	[0; 20] and [60; 100]	[1E-07; 1E-06]
Median	62	4E-07
Mean	50	4E-06
Trimmed mean	75 (2 nd mode)	1E-06 (excluding extremes)
Lower quartile	[0; 4]	[0; 3E-08]
Interquartile range	[4; 84]	[3E-08; 9E-07]
Upper quartile	[84;120]	[9E-07; 1E-03]

5.3.2.2. Resource use, fossil

In the case of fossil resources and uranium, the calculation is relatively straightforward, as the characterization factor corresponds solely to the net calorific value (LHV). Therefore, for the same quantity of resource extracted, the contribution is higher for those with greater energy content. For example, the consumption of 1 kg of crude oil (42 MJ/kg average) contributes approximately four times more than 1 kg of peat (10 MJ/kg). However, extending this comparison further does not provide meaningful insights for two reasons. First, when fossils are consumed as energy carriers, their value lies in their heating capacity; therefore, those with lower LHV are consumed in greater quantities to meet energy demand. Second, when used as feedstock, the contribution is determined by their material properties rather than their LHV.

Approximately 88 % of the carbon content in chemicals is fossil-based, indicating the predominance of fossil raw materials. In addition, the chemical industry depends heavily on fossil fuels for energy supply. As a result, a high impact in this subcategory is common in the chemical sector, particularly in the adhesives industry. The relative frequency histogram for this category displays a clear bimodal distribution skewed to the left. The first peak, with values below 20 MJ/kg, corresponds to substances that are not fossil-based and whose manufacturing processes do not require significant fossil energy inputs. Examples include inorganic materials such as silica and calcium carbonate, as well as biomass products like natural rubber latex. The second peak, concentrated between 60 and 100 MJ/kg and approximating a normal distribution, corresponds to substances that either use fossil feedstocks or involve energy-intensive processes, which are prevalent in this industry.

In the case of bimodal graphs, the mean and median provide limited insight. Here, the trimmed mean (75 MJ/kg), calculated for values around the second peak, offers a more relevant reference for comparing substances. Most common raw materials in the adhesives industry can be found around this value. Quartiles further help categorize extreme and average values: substances below 4 MJ/kg typically lack fossil feedstocks or significant fossil energy consumption, while those above 84 MJ/kg are purely fossil-based and/or require energy-intensive processes. Substances within these limits, in the interquartile range, represent the average cases.

Two main production aspects notably increase results in this subcategory:

- Hydrocarbon feedstocks: Refinery products such as monomers, organic solvents, and resins are the base materials in most specialty chemicals and adhesives. For instance, solvent-based adhesives tend to have higher impacts than water-based alternatives. Most fossil-based polymers fall into this category.
- Energy-intensive processes: Thermal operations, such as drying or thermal cracking, are often powered by non-renewable energy, significantly contributing to the impact. Compounds based on isocyanates and silicones are characteristic examples.

Additional considerations include:

- Results may vary for the same substance when calculated for different regions, given their dependence on the local energy mix.
- The portion of the indicator attributable to fossil fuels combusted as energy carriers is closely linked to the Product Carbon Footprint (PCF). Consequently, a high RU, fossil indicator is usually associated with an elevated PCF. However, the correlation between these two indicators is not complete. First, fossil resources that remain embedded within products during the study's scope are not released as carbon emissions and therefore do not contribute to the PCF. Second, although fossil fuel combustion is the primary source of GHG emissions in industry, the relationship between the fossil resource's energy content and its contribution to global warming potential is not straightforward. This can be related to process efficiencies, side reactions, and the fact that different gases have different global warming potentials. Moreover, some industrial processes—such as limestone calcination in clinker production—generate CO₂ as a by-product and thus contribute substantially to the PCF, independently of fossil fuel use.
- Biobased products, such as soy-based polyester resin (Figure 2) or non-ionic biobased surfactants, can exhibit unexpectedly high RU, fossil values, sometimes close to or exceeding those of fossil-based products. This can be explained by the energy demand of biomass pretreatment and conversion processes (e.g., steam explosion, organosolvation) and by transport-related fossil fuel consumption, depending on the distance between raw material sources and production sites.

5.3.2.3. *Resource use, minerals and metals*

For the minerals and metals subcategory, results depend on multiple factors. The indicator is directly proportional to the global extraction rate—meaning that widely demanded resources exert greater environmental pressure—and inversely proportional to availability, meaning that scarce resources lead to higher impact scores.

In

Figure 9, several elements are shown with their corresponding characterization factors (CFs), which enable comparative analysis. These values indicate how the impact would differ if, for example, 1 kg of each element were extracted. The reference substance, Sb, is highlighted for comparison.

The first five elements listed are the most impactful metals; only these have CFs greater than or equal to 1. These elements are either extremely scarce, highly demanded, or both. Particular attention should be paid to the inventory of catalyst consumption in the early stages of the study, since many catalysts are based on these highly contributing metals. In contrast, many metals exhibit CFs several orders of magnitude lower than 1, some as low as 10^{-11} . Some elements, such as calcium, are so abundant on Earth that their contribution is not even considered, no CF is assigned to them.

A selection of metals commonly used in the adhesives industry is also presented. Tin, for example, is used as a catalyst in adhesives' production. Sodium is the most common element in neutralization reactants, and iron is used in multiple ways such as pigment. In general, adhesives do not contain large amounts of metals; their use is mostly limited to additives and catalysts. By contrast, certain minerals are used in significant quantities as fillers or inorganic binders (e.g., calcium carbonate, gypsum and cement). However, their abundance results in extremely low CFs for their constituting elements, and therefore negligible contributions to the indicator. This explains why the overall impact in this subcategory is typically low.

Figure 9. Main contributors and other widely used metals.

Important methodological clarification: Most data were extracted from the Ecoinvent 3.11 database. For the same substance, datasets are available for different regions, differing mainly in the energy mix. In this study, RER (Europe) and RoW (Rest of the World) datasets were compared. Significant inconsistencies were identified in RU, metals and minerals results, where values expressed in kg Sb eq. were not consistent with the technologies represented. Differences were particularly pronounced in RoW datasets, sometimes reaching up to one order of magnitude compared to RER. These inconsistencies were traced primarily to sulfuric acid production datasets.

Sulfuric acid, a key input in petroleum refining, fertilizer production, and surfactant manufacturing, is represented in Ecoinvent as a market mix. The elevated Sb eq. value arises from a single dataset from China, where sulfuric acid is modelled as a by-product of copper concentrate smelting. In practice, copper is not consumed in significant quantities for sulfuric acid production, and this pathway is not representative of the dominant synthetic routes. The discrepancy between sulfuric acid produced via copper smelting and average production datasets reaches 3 to 4 orders of magnitude. As a result, despite its relatively minor share in the market, this dataset introduces a substantial distortion. Its inclusion in the market mix therefore inflates results for most raw materials. To avoid this effect, the analyses in this study focus on European datasets, which are less influenced by this distortion, although not entirely independent from it.

Consequently, practitioners must be cautious when interpreting this indicator, as results may not fully reflect reality. Trends in RU, metals and minerals are strongly influenced by sulfuric acid consumption rather than by the actual extraction of metals and minerals in manufacturing processes.

As presented in Table 5, results for this category span several orders of magnitude, from $1\text{E}-10$ to $1\text{E}-03$ kg Sb eq. The relative frequency histogram shows a unimodal distribution approximating a normal curve. The main peak lies between $1\text{E}-07$ and $1\text{E}-06$ kg Sb eq., close to the trimmed mean ($1\text{E}-06$ kg Sb eq.) calculated by excluding extreme values. Based on quartiles, very low values fall below $3\text{E}-08$ kg Sb eq., while very high values exceed $9\text{E}-07$ kg Sb eq., with most raw materials lying in between.

Additional remarks:

- Silicone products, such as silyl-modified polymers, show high impacts in this category due to copper consumption in their production, as well as tin use as a catalyst.
- Lithium carbonate exhibits the highest impact, but this is mainly attributed to the sulfuric acid dataset described above and therefore not realistic.
- Vinyl acetate production typically involves gold catalysts, leading to high impacts for this substance and its derivatives, such as ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA).
- For non-ionic surfactants, the trend observed in RU, fossils is reversed: the biobased surfactant (derived from fatty acids) has a higher impact than the fossil-based alternative, probably due to the metal consumption associated with fertilizer production.

These analyses highlight the importance of careful interpretation of results. Understanding the processes and the contribution of each metal (as shown in Figure 9) enables solid strategic decisions during the design phase. For instance, there is growing interest in phasing out tin catalysts in silicone and polyurethane production due to toxicity concerns [32]. However, some proposed alternatives considered safe, such as platinum, are scarce metals that would increase impacts in the category under analysis. This illustrates a clear case of burden shifting.

5.3.2.4. Correlation between raw materials and product impact

Based on Figure 5 and Figure 6, it is possible to analyse the relationship between the environmental impacts of adhesives and those of the raw materials used in their formulation.

As noted at the beginning of this section, the product impacts account not only for raw material supply but also for transport and manufacturing. Therefore, the product impact is not a simple arithmetic sum of the raw materials' contributions. Nonetheless, the overall impact is still largely determined by formulation, as demonstrated by the fact that product results for RU, fossils follow the same trend as their corresponding binders.

In contrast, the inconsistency observed for RU, minerals and metals make it unreliable to draw conclusions in this category. The correlation is therefore examined primarily for fossil resource use.

For example, the group of adhesives and sealants used for floor preparation—mainly composed of inorganic binders and fillers and referred to as “inorganic-based” in the graphs—shows the lowest impact. Conversely, the silane-modified polymer adhesive presents the highest impact, consistent with the silyl-modified polymer that constitutes its main raw material. The main binder on the formulations appears to be guiding the overall tendency on the product group.

It is also noteworthy that, although the same overall trend is observed, the fossil resource impact of products is significantly lower than that of their corresponding raw materials. This reduction can be explained by the “dilution” effect of fillers in powder dispersions and water in solvent-based adhesives. Regarding additives, although they show high average RU, fossils, their contribution remains low due to the small quantities in which they are used.

6. Conclusion

This thesis has explored the complexities of evaluating the “Resource Use” impact category within the adhesives industry, using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) as the primary framework. The study combined a critical methodological review with a statistical analysis of common raw materials and products, providing insights that are relevant not only to adhesives but also to the broader chemical sector. Understanding the different contributions to the indicators and its relationship with the formulation and process energy-demand is crucial to support eco-design.

As expected for an industry closely related to petrochemicals, RU, fossils proved to be significant in the adhesives’ industry. Contrarily, the assessment of RU, minerals and metals proved to be highly unstable and unreliable due to inconsistencies in the database. The study exposed the need to be cautious at the moment of drawing conclusions based on the results for both categories. Nonetheless, it must be highlighted that, despite the inherent uncertainties in LCA, the knowledge gained about processes, raw materials, and supply chains can meaningfully guide sustainable decision-making. Most environmental indicators from EF 3.1, and specifically RU, have potential to add significant value to industrial LCAs but they still require further methodological development to reach the reliability of the Product Carbon Footprint. Incorporating these indicators into assessments, reflecting on the representativeness of results, and verifying their alignment with real-world practices are steps that will enhance their implementation.

A key outline is the need to consider a wider range of impact categories. Focusing exclusively on climate change leads to overlooking opportunities to select better raw materials and improve overall resource efficiency—factors that play a critical role in a product’s environmental footprint. Moreover, limiting the attention to GHGs emissions can inadvertently cause “burden shifting,” which occurs when one environmental concern is solved while another is created.

All things considered, performing comprehensive LCAs is essential for promoting sustainable manufacturing in the adhesives industry, even though methodological and practical obstacles still exist. LCA’s protagonism in accomplishing genuine sustainability goals will be further strengthened by ongoing efforts to enhance data quality, improve impact assessment methodologies, and provide solid interpretation references.

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